

EXTRACTION OF BISMUTH FROM POLYMETALLIC ORES: METHODS, CHALLENGES, AND PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT. Bismuth (Bi) is a critical metal with applications in pharmaceuticals, electronics, and green technologies. Due to its scarcity in nature, efficient recovery from polymetallic ores (e.g., lead, copper, and tin concentrates) is essential. This review examines current hydrometallurgical, pyrometallurgical, and electrometallurgical techniques for bismuth extraction, focusing on selective leaching, solvent extraction, and electrolytic refining. Challenges, such as low recovery rates and environmental concerns, are discussed, along with emerging bioleaching and membrane separation methods. The paper outlines future research directions to improve sustainability and economic viability.

Key words: bismuth recovery, polymetallic ores, sustainability.

ИЗВЛИЧАНЕ НА БИСМУТ ОТ ПОЛИМЕТАЛНИ РУДИ: МЕТОДИ, ПРЕДИЗВИКАТЕЛСТВА И БЪДЕЩИ НАСОКИ

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Бисмутът (Bi) е критичен метал с приложения във фармацевтиката, електрониката и зелените технологии. Поради неговата рядкост, ефективното му извличане от полиметални руди (напр. оловни, медни и калаени концентрати) е от съществено значение. Този обзор разглежда съвременните хидрометалургични, пирометалургични и електрометалургични техники за извличане на бисмут, като се фокусира върху селективното излужване, екстракцията с разтворител и електролитно рафиниране. Обсъждат се предизвикателства като ниските нива на извличане и екологичните проблеми, както и нововъзникващите методи за биоизлужване и мембранно разделяне. Статията представя и бъдещи насоки на изследванията за подобряване на устойчивостта и икономическата ефективност.

Ключови думи: извличане на бисмут, полиметални руди, устойчивост.

Introduction

The world economy and industry and their requirements have changed over time. The transition towards a green and sustainable economy has increased the demand for some specific raw materials needed for the production of solar cells and batteries (Rhaman et al., 2021). Shifting the emphasis toward these materials and the present geopolitical situation in the world affecting the supply chain lead to the creation of the Critical Raw Materials Act. Demand for Bi is increasing, mostly as a non-toxic substitute for Pb in chemicals. Bismuth is primarily recovered as a byproduct of lead, copper, and tungsten processing. Polymetallic ores often contain Bi in concentrations of 0.1–5%, necessitating selective extraction methods. Growing demand for Bi in low-melting alloys, catalysts, and radiation shielding underscores the need for efficient recovery technologies (Liu and Handschuh-Wang, 2025). Bismuth was classified as a critical raw material by the European Commission in 2017 and a critical mineral by the USA in 2018. Bi is traditionally used in medicine as an ingredient in some drugs, in cosmetics as a pigment in paint for eye shadows, hair sprays, and nail polish, in electronics, and for alloys as non-toxic substitute for lead. A new emerging application of Bi has reawakened interest in its production and supply. Reports on development of Bi-based batteries have been published (Phung et al., 2024), showing successful synthesis of novel $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3@ \text{NaBi}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ nanocomposites (NCs) – comprising integrated Bi_2O_3 and $\text{NaBi}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ nanostructures – and their evaluation as anode materials for lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) for the first time. By optimising the reaction time, the authors managed to precisely control the NCs' morphology, composition, and phase state. These NC-based anodes demonstrate exceptional electrochemical performance in LIBs,

including: high reversible capacity ($1052 \text{ mAh} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ for $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3@ \text{NaBi}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ -1h and $1034 \text{ mAh} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ for $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3@ \text{NaBi}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$ -3h after 200 cycles); outstanding capacity retention (110% and 129%, respectively) and superior rate capability, long cycle life, low charge-transfer resistance, and pseudocapacitive behaviour. The research in that area is ever increasing and Yang et al. (2025) published a review summarising the current progress of Bi-based materials in nickel bismuth batteries as viable alternatives to traditional lithium-ion batteries, offering enhanced safety, eco-friendliness, and cost-efficiency. Man et al. (2025) also reported on the prospect of bismuth and its compounds in sodium-ion batteries. This review examines promising anode material candidates for sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), with particular focus on bismuth-based anodes. These materials distinguish themselves through their exceptional theoretical capacity and comparatively low volume expansion relative to other alloy-type anodes. The analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of bismuth's sodium storage mechanisms, employing both *ex-situ* structural characterisations and density functional theory (DFT) calculations. An explanation for the remarkable rate capability of bismuth metal anodes was provided and it underscores why they have become a preferred choice among battery researchers.

Another novel perspective field where bismuth finds its application is as a materials for the photocatalytic reduction of both organic and inorganic pollutants (Perumal et al., 2022; Kumar et al. 2024). Sun et al. (2023) summarised the available data for the photocatalytic reduction of hexavalent chromium in water. The review highlights significant advancements in enhancing the photocatalytic Cr(VI) reduction efficiency of Bi-based materials through established modification approaches, including heterojunction formation, elemental doping, and defect tuning. Performance evaluation revealed that hierarchically

nanostructured BiVO_4 with optimised particle sizes (5–10 nm) exhibits superior catalytic activity among Bi-based materials. The unique “shuriken”-like morphology of BiVO_4 enhances light harvesting through efficient multiple reflections and scattering. Comparative analysis demonstrates that BiVO_4 outperforms other promising photocatalysts like Ag@TiO_2 in Cr(VI) reduction, highlighting the potential of Bi-based materials in this field.

But still, practical implementation faces substantial challenges. It was estimated that under ideal conditions (100% collection efficiency), reducing 1 mole of Cr(VI) to Cr(III) would require a minimum solar array area exceeding 5000 m^2 (>6000 MJ energy input). This result indicates that current Bi-based materials remain insufficient for real-world aqueous Cr(VI) remediation.

Tabassum et al. (2025) investigated bismuth oxyhalides (BiOX) as a highly promising class of photocatalysts, attracting widespread attention due to their unique layered structure and versatile applications in energy conversion. These nanomaterials exhibit exceptional physicochemical properties, including facet-dependent internal electric fields (IEFs), pH-responsive crystal facet exposure, and phase transitions. Their distinctive layered architecture further enhances their potential for environmental remediation. A key advantage of BiOX photocatalysts lies in their reusability, as demonstrated by their stability over multiple reaction cycles – a critical factor that sets them apart from many conventional catalysts.

Major Suppliers of the EU's Critical Raw Materials Needs

Share in percent of critical raw materials needed by the EU from select countries.

Source: European Commission, Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU 2023 - Final Report | BertelsmannStiftung

Fig. 1. Major Suppliers of the EU's Critical Raw Materials Needs (Source: European Commission, Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU 2023 - Final Report)

Despite significant progress in energy production and environmental applications, challenges remain in optimising BiOX for large-scale deployment. Most reported BiOX-based systems are still confined to laboratory settings, necessitating further research to bridge the gap between fundamental studies and real-world implementation. Given their low toxicity, layered morphology, and exceptional photocatalytic efficiency, BiOX materials hold immense promise for industrial-scale applications.

Deady et al. (2022) investigated thoroughly the bismuth geology and chain of supply. They surmised that the global supply chain has significantly localised graphically, with primary production centered at Asia (Vietnam's Núi Pháo mine and as a byproduct of lead and tungsten processing in China).

This constrained supply framework has created complete import dependence for major economies; e.g. the European Union requires 100% of its high-purity ($\geq 99.8\%$) refined bismuth imports to meet industrial demand and the United States has

maintained total import reliance since 1997 following the closure of its last primary bismuth refinery. These supply chain vulnerabilities, combined with current end-of-life recycling rates (which remain below 1%), collectively contribute to bismuth's classification as a critical raw material across multiple strategic assessments.

Bismuth minerals found in hydrothermal and magmatic environments typically occur in four principal categories: native bismuth and its alloys with gold and silver; sulfides and sulfosalts including bismuthinite (Bi_2S_3); oxides (bismite) and oxysalts, such as bismutite [$(\text{BiO})_2\text{CO}_3$]; and selenides and tellurides (tellurobismuthite).

Bismuthinite is the most significant primary bismuth ore, though substantial quantities are also extracted from Bi-bearing galena deposits. Gold and bismuth are frequently distributed similarly during ore formation processes. Bismuth is mainly obtained as a byproduct during the mining of lead (Pb), tungsten (W), copper (Cu), or gold (Au), with its extraction techniques varying according to the ore's mineralogical characteristics. Despite being a frequent component alongside these more abundant metals, bismuth often remains as waste in many mining operations. Some of the most common sources for Bi are: lead concentrates (Pb-Bi) forming a major source (~60%) of global Bi production; copper smelter flue dust, which contains Bi_2O_3 and Bi_2S_3 ; and tin processing residues (Bi-Sn alloys in solder scrap).

Conventional methods for extraction

Hydrometallurgical processes

Acid leaching. Bismuth was successfully recovered by leaching from HCl solution using copper powder as an alternative to conventional hydrolysis. It was based on the extraction of bismuth (Bi^{3+}) from a hydrochloric acid (HCl) system by cementation with copper (Cu^0) powder (Shen et al., 2019). Thermodynamic and cyclic voltammetry (CV) analyses were performed to confirm the spontaneous nature of the cementation reaction between Cu^0 and Bi^{3+} . Batch experiments conducted in order to find the optimal conditions demonstrated 99% bismuth recovery under the following parameters: HCl concentration 6 mol L^{-1} , temperature 60°C, $\text{Cu}^0/\text{Bi}^{3+}$ molar ratio 4, stirring rate 500 rpm, and reaction time 30 min. It is important to keep in mind that arsenic (As) and antimony (Sb) impurities inhibit cementation due to the predominant formation of Cu_2Sb and Cu_3As intermetallics. It was found that $\text{Cu}^0/\text{Bi}^{3+}$ cementation followed first-order kinetics between 20–60°C, with an activation energy of 8.58 kJ mol^{-1} , indicating a diffusion-controlled process. Bi is dissolved as BiCl_3 ($\text{pH} < 1$), while impurities (Pb, Cu) precipitate as sulphates or chlorides.

Recovered bismuth consisted of bulk crystalline particles (elemental Bi). Residual Cu^+ in the solution was recovered as copper sulfides via deep sulphidation, suitable for direct copper smelting. This highlights the potential of Cu^0 cementation for sustainable Bi^{3+} extraction.

In another study, a hydrometallurgical process was developed for the simultaneous recovery of bismuth and arsenic from copper smelter flue dusts using H_2SO_4 -NaCl solution (Chen et al., 2012). The dusts were first leached using the above

mentioned solution, achieving high extraction efficiencies of approximately 95% for bismuth and 88% for arsenic. The dissolved bismuth and arsenic were subsequently separated through an alkaline leaching step, which proved highly effective, resulting in arsenic separation of ~97% transferred into the alkaline solution, while more than 99.5% of bismuth remained in the solid residue.

After additional refining, valuable products like arsenic-rich alkaline solution were processed into sodium arsenate and the bismuth-containing residue was converted to sponge bismuth (purity >90%). As an overall result, the recovery rates reached ~90% for bismuth and ~42% for arsenic. The major advantages of the process that are worth mentioning are the high selectivity in bismuth-arsenic separation and the value-added product generation (sodium arsenate and high-purity sponge bismuth). The H_2SO_4 -NaCl leaching system demonstrated excellent metal extraction efficiency and the integrated approach offers a sustainable solution for recovering critical metals from copper smelting by-products while minimising waste generation.

Alkaline leaching. A novel method for alkaline pressure oxidative leaching process has been developed by He et al. (2019) which effectively removes arsenic (As), antimony (Sb), and lead (Pb) from bismuth-rich and arsenic-rich lead anode slimes, while simultaneously enriching with bismuth (Bi), gold (Au), and silver (Ag). The authors investigated the effect of temperature, liquid-to-solid (L/S) ratio, leaching time, and reagent concentration effects and established the optimal conditions: leaching time 2 hours, L/S ratio 7:1, NaNO_3 addition - 20 wt% of slime mass, temperature 180°C, NaOH concentration 150 g/L, and agitation speed 300 rpm. The follow-up analysis revealed removal efficiencies of 95.36% for arsenic, 79.98% for antimony, and 63.08% for lead. XRD characterisation revealed that the leaching residue primarily contains metallic bismuth (Bi), bismuth oxide (Bi_2O_3), lead antimonate ($\text{Pb}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_7$), as well as trace amounts of sodium hexahydroxoantimonate ($\text{NaSb}(\text{OH})_6$). Lead and arsenic have been removed as the complex compounds of sodium arsenate decahydrate ($\text{Na}_3\text{AsO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and lead antimonate ($\text{Pb}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{O}_7$). Using XPS analysis confirmed increasing yields of high-valence Sb and Pb species with NaNO_3 addition since the oxidative environment (maintained by NaNO_3) proved crucial for achieving high removal efficiencies. This method provides an effective separation of impurity elements (As, Sb, Pb) from valuable metals (Bi, Au, Ag) and fine oxidation state control through reagent addition. The process represents a significant advancement in the treatment of complex anode slimes, offering improved metal recovery and purification capabilities. As one can summarise, the alkaline medium (NaOH) facilitated selective dissolution of target impurities and both temperature and agitation play critical role for reaction kinetics.

Solvent extraction (SX). A systematic approach was developed by Yang et al. (2009) for the selective separation and co-extraction of bismuth (Bi) and molybdenum (Mo) from low-grade bismuth glance concentrate. The integrated process comprises the following key stages: hydrochloric acid leaching (initial dissolution of target metals), purification and deoxidisation (removal of impurities and redox conditioning), solvent extraction (Bi) (selective recovery of bismuth using N235

extractant), lime roasting (conversion of Mo into a leachable form), leaching and solvent extraction (Mo), and final recovery of molybdenum. Each stage was optimised to maximise collective recovery efficiency. Solvent extraction with N235 achieved over 99% Bi recovery and over 98% Mo recovery. N235 is tertiary amine with general formula R_3N where $\text{R} = \text{C}_8\text{--}\text{C}_{10}$. This trialkyl (R_3N) amine is a widely-used extractant for the extraction of Zn, rare earth, molybdenum, and vanadium. Process conditions were fine-tuned for high selectivity and yield, demonstrating industrial feasibility.

Moriya et al. (2001) examined the extraction behaviour of bismuth(III) with 2-bromoalkanoic acids in non-donating solvents. Since the extraction mechanisms of bismuth(III) using carboxylic acids (HL) have remained unclear due to complications from hydroxide precipitation, it was investigated in both benzene and hexane systems under highly acidic aqueous conditions ($\text{I} = 1.0 \text{ M } (\text{H,Li})\text{NO}_3$). The extraction equilibria were systematically analysed by examining nitric acid concentration effects and bismuth(III) distribution in the organic phase. It was identified that benzene exclusively formed $\text{BiL}_3(\text{HL})_3$ complexes, while hexane facilitated both monomeric ($\text{BiL}_3(\text{HL})_4$) and oligomeric ($\text{Bi}_3\text{L}_9\text{HL}$) species. Despite the investigation, the underlying reason for this solvent-specific speciation still remains unclear. This work successfully demonstrates the liquid-liquid extraction of bismuth(III) using 2-bromoalkanoic acid/non-donating solvent systems while effectively preventing hydroxide precipitation. The solvent-dependent speciation patterns provide new insights into the complexation behavior of Bi(III) with carboxylic acid extractants.

Pyrometallurgical methods

Smelting. The Kroll-Betterton process represents a metallurgical technique for purifying lead bullion through the removal of bismuth and antimony contaminants. This refining method operates by introducing calcium and magnesium into molten lead (typically at ~380°C), where they form high-melting-point intermetallic compounds (notably CaMg_2Bi_2) with the impurities (Gupta, 2003). These solidified compounds separate as a surface dross that can be physically removed, enabling production of lead with exceptionally low bismuth concentrations (<0.01%). It targets residual bismuth/antimony removal after prior extraction of precious metals (Au, Ag) and copper and enables bismuth recovery via subsequent chlorination of skimmed dross. The method proves particularly valuable when processing lead bullion requiring strict bismuth control while maintaining cost efficiency compared to electrochemical approaches. The skimmed byproducts retain value through potential bismuth reclamation. Mallaley et al. (1990) presented an investigation of bismuth removal via the Kroll-Betterton Process through calcium and magnesium treatment. It was observed that the mass ratio of calcium to magnesium can be adjusted to minimise overall processing expenses while maintaining effective bismuth removal. The metal losses occur primarily through particle abrasion during dissolution in the molten lead, and bismuth recontamination happens when processed bullion contacts residual crust material during bailing operations. At approximately 320°C, the measured concentrations of bismuth, calcium, and magnesium in the bullion yield a solubility product value that closely matches established literature data. Their study demonstrates that while the Kroll-Betterton process effectively reduces bismuth content, process optimisation requires careful consideration of metal

ratios and operational parameters to minimise costs and maximise efficiency.

Electrometallurgy

Electrorefining. Hernández-Pérez et al. (2024) studied the selective electrodeposition of antimony and bismuth from highly concentrated hydrochloric acid solutions, which simulate the composition of ion exchange resin eluates used in purifying spent electrorefining baths. Preliminary voltammetric analysis revealed that the small difference between the reduction potentials of antimony and bismuth makes their separate recovery extremely difficult. This finding was supported by potentiostatic electrolysis tests conducted at low cathodic potentials (e.g., -0.25V vs. Ag/AgCl), below bismuth's reduction potential.

At current densities exceeding 1mA cm^{-2} , selectivity and current efficiency for antimony deposition declined sharply due to increased cathodic potentials, promoting bismuth deposition and hydrogen evolution. Galvanostatic tests with varying antimony-bismuth ratios showed that higher bismuth concentrations improved its deposition efficiency but reduced selectivity. At high current densities (4.5mA cm^{-2}), elevated cathodic potentials favoured the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) when bismuth levels were low. In contrast, with abundant bismuth, overall electrodeposition efficiencies exceeded 75%, though unselective co-deposition occurred.

Green method for extraction of Bi and Pb

Most of the traditional methods of separating bismuth-rich melt from the fire smelting of Bi slags have a number of disadvantages. They can be harmful to the environment and have a low recovery rate of metals. They pose a number of risks to human health and contain a series of complex operations. This necessitates the search for a new green approach, like the extraction of Bi and Pb from the bismuth-rich melt by supergravity. This method has a number of advantages, such as high separation efficiency, continuous operation, no emission of waste residues, effluents, and dust, which are expected to provide a new direction for green extraction of Bi and Pb from the bismuth-rich melt (Wen et al., 2020).

Emerging Technologies

Membrane Separation

Polymer inclusion membranes (PIMs). Polymer inclusion membranes (PIMs) represent a significant advancement in the development of sustainable separation, recovery, and analytical techniques for environmentally and economically valuable species. Beyond the apparent benefits of liquid membranes, PIMs offer superior stability compared to supported liquid membranes (SLMs). This enhanced stability arises from the structure of membrane components within the polymer matrix, as opposed to the pore-based capillary forces that govern SLMs.

A key advantage of PIMs is their tunable extraction properties, which can be tailored by adjusting the composition and ratio of their primary constituents: the base polymer and the extractant. In certain formulations, the choice and concentration of plasticiser further influence membrane performance by enhancing mechanical properties and improving compatibility

among components. This adaptability makes PIMs a versatile and efficient platform for advanced separation processes. Ghaderi et al. (2021) reported the development of a novel polymer inclusion membrane (PIM) for efficient bismuth(III) extraction from hydrochloric acid solutions. The optimised membrane composition consisted of 40 wt% cellulose triacetate (CTA) as base polymer, 25 wt% trioctylamine (TOA) as extractant and 35 wt% tri-*n*-butyl phosphate (TBP) as plasticiser. Contact angle measurements confirmed appropriate membrane hydrophobicity and stress-strain tests demonstrated that TBP/TOA addition significantly improved membrane elasticity and reduced tensile strength compared to pure CTA films.

Extraction performance of the novel PIM achieved quantitative Bi(III) extraction (from 20 mg/L solutions in 0.3 M HCl) using 3.5 cm diameter PIM segments, 120 min contact time, and 160 rpm orbital shaking. The proposed extraction mechanism primarily involved $[\text{TOAH}^+]_2[\text{BiCl}_5^{2-}]$ ion-pair formation. Effective Bi(III) stripping (99% recovery) using a 2 M Na_2CO_3 solution was observed. The PIM demonstrated exceptional selectivity for Bi(III) over the competing metal ions (Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Mo^{6+} , W^{6+}) and anionic species (SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^-), while outperformed PVC/DEHPA membranes in Fe(III)/Bi(III) separation. The membrane maintained its composition through 4 extraction/stripping cycles and substituting TBP with NPOE or DBP extended stability to ≥ 10 cycles.

The PIM developed in this study showed strong potential for bismuth recovery from industrial streams, offering high selectivity, effective regeneration, and adaptability through plasticiser optimisation.

Supported liquid membranes (SLMs). Supported liquid membranes (SLM) for recovery of bismuth from aqueous solutions was reported by Reyes-Aguilera et al. (2008). The liquid-liquid extraction experiments revealed that each mole of Bi(III) interacts with two moles of Cyanex 921 (tri-*n*-octylphosphine oxide (TOPO) extractant) in the solvated complex extracted into the organic phase. Additionally, the recovery of Bi(III) using a supported liquid membrane (SLM) was found to be viable. Introducing HCl to the feed solution supplies chloride ions, which combine with Bi(III) to form neutral complexes, thereby enhancing SLM performance. Optimal Bi(III) recovery rates were achieved with a 0.5 M HCl concentration in the feed solution. Cyanex 921 was identified as a suitable extractant for Bi(III) recovery via SLM, as it does not require high concentrations to achieve efficient extraction – yielding recovery rates as high as 90%.

Hybrid Processes

Leaching-SX-Electrowinning. A combined chloride leaching and electrowinning method was developed by Che et al. (2020) for the selective extraction of bismuth from Pb-Bi slag. Thermodynamic studies revealed a notable solubility difference between PbSO_4 and Bi_2O_3 in chloride media. A detailed investigation was then conducted to assess the influence of different parameters on bismuth leaching efficiency using HCl- CaCl_2 solutions. The results demonstrated that Bi leaching was primarily affected by CaCl_2 concentration and the liquid-to-solid (L/S) ratio, while temperature and reaction time had minimal impact. The optimal leaching conditions were identified as 100 g/L CaCl_2 , an L/S ratio of 4 mL/g, a temperature of 50°C , and a duration of 1 hour.

Following leaching, bismuth recovery from the solution was examined via electrowinning. Cyclic voltammetry measurements established the reduction potential for Bi at -0.239 V. The experiments showed that high-purity metallic bismuth (99.5%) could be achieved at 50°C with a cathode current density of 150 A/m^2 , yielding a current efficiency of approximately 85.46%. Based on these findings, a closed-loop process was proposed for efficient bismuth recovery from Pb-Bi slag.

Challenges

Although it has significant applications in biology, medicine, and industry, it is important to consider the biological impact of bismuth and the residual products of its production. Bismuth is considered to be nontoxic (15 g can be tolerated by an adult), but the long-term use of bismuth may result in side effects and even toxicity to humans. There are a few cases caused by occupational exposure to bismuth in the manufacturing industry, but most of the poisoning incidents occur in the form of accidental over-dosage of bismuth drugs. The toxicity of bismuth depends on both the individual case and the type of compound and its amount (Yang & Sun, 2011).

Bismuth(III) occurs in different chemical forms: from metal to oxides, hydroxides, and various inorganic salts, such as nitrate, phosphate, sulphide, sulphate, carbonate, orthosilicates, halides, and others. In solutions, its salts undergo extensive hydrolysis, forming oxy compounds and polynuclear aggregates, and these compounds exhibit flexible coordination geometries, leading to a broad spectrum of applications, from alloys and metallurgic additives to thermo- and ferroelectric materials, pigments, and catalysts (Mehring, 2016). Bismuth is both non-toxic and relatively inexpensive heavy metal, it is used in place of other related heavy metals (as a substitute for lead in plumbing fixtures) (Carlin, 2011). Bi^{3+} salts are used for medical purposes, mainly because of their acid–base, antibacterial, and antiviral properties (Briand & Burford, 1999) They are considered non-toxic, ecologically friendly, easy to work with, and insensitive to water and air (Cunha et al., 2002). Recent studies of the physicochemical properties of Bi compounds have resulted in the synthesis of Bi-based materials with different crystallographic structures and with micro- and nanometer sizes.

Perspectives

A constant need for cost-efficient and sustainable methods for critical raw materials like bismuth drives the efforts of researcher towards the development of new superior methods for extraction. Some of them include promising new perspectives, like ionic liquid leaching (Emam & El-Hefny, 2023), biorecovery (Saddique et al., 2023) and circular economy (Granvik et al., 2025).

Conclusion

While conventional methods dominate Bi recovery, innovations in solvent extraction and bioleaching promise cleaner, more efficient alternatives. Future work should optimise hybrid processes and reduce reliance on harsh reagents. Reducing the consumption and emphasising on the recycling will also benefit the price and availability of bismuth.

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